

GROW: Development and Effectiveness of a Positive Intervention to Improve Mental Health in Individuals Within Educational Organizations

Ana Blasco-Belled, Claudia Tejada-Gallardo and Carles Alsinet

Universitat de Lleida

Purpose

In recent years there has been an exponential growth in studies focused on the promotion of mental health in educational organizations. The third sustainable development goal (UN General Assembly, 2015) states "guarantee healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages." With this objective, it is sought to eliminate the disparity in well-being, and has given rise to initiatives and strategies that focus on the educational population. Following the understanding of mental health as formed by two indicators (i.e., presence of well-being and absence of psychological distress), it can be assumed that the reduction of psychological distress is not only necessary for having a complete state of mental health but also the promotion and enhancement of well-being (Keyes, 2009). Traditionally, psychologists have focused their attention on the prevention and treatment of disease and impaired functioning, leaving aside the other side of the coin (i.e., well-being). However, the development of positive psychology as a science yielded new approaches of intervention aiming at fostering well-being in different settings such as the educational in order to upskill individuals in mental health management and prevent them from future psychological problems (Simonton & Baumeister, 2005). The GROW program (Gaining Resources for Optimal Well-being) has as main objective promoting well-being. This program has proved its effectiveness in different contextual groups (e.g., children, adolescents, youth at risk, educational professionals). The program is based on fundamentals of positive psychology and is considered a multi-component program to promote different types of well-being (hedonic and eudaimonic) and positive feelings towards the present, past, and future. This program will be included within a mentoring training for master and PhD students in the Universitat de Lleida (Spain) for the next course in order to promote mentors' mental health and also provide them with the necessary tools to implement the program to future mentees.

Design

The program consists of 8 weekly sessions consisting of 1 hour and a half each. Different aspects of well-being are worked: (1) introductory session about well-being, (2) strengths, (3) positive emotions, (4) forgiveness, (5) gratitude, (6) optimism, (7) hope, and (8) goal setting.

Measurement

The survey will be the same that we previously administered to other groups. It is designed to explore the sociodemographic profile of the participants, their mental health, including measures of well-being and psychological distress and finally, we also assessed personality traits. The survey will be sent to master and doctoral students through an e-mail from the unit in charge of the mentoring training. Different validated scales will be administered:

1. Psychological well-being (PWBS; Ryff, 1989).
2. Social well-being (SWBS; Keyes, 1998).
3. Satisfaction with life (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985).
4. Positive and negative experiences (SPANE; Diener & Biswas-Diener, 2009).
5. Depression, anxiety, and stress (DASS-21; Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995).
6. Personality (Benet-Martínez & John, 1998).

Statistical Analysis

The impact of the program in previous groups has been analyzed through different statistical methodologies, for instance, linear general models, latent profile transition analyses, and network analysis. However, the mentoring program that will be applied to master and PhD students has not started yet so we do not have sample characteristics and an analysis plan prepared for now.

Results (if applicable)

The GROW program in other groups has shown an improvement in well-being of participants, especially in eudaimonic well-being (psychological and social). Even so, differences between groups (intervention and control) have also been observed in subjective well-being (positive affect and subjective well-being). We cannot provide results for the mentoring program for now but we hypothesize that the future results will be in line with previous findings.

Implications

The promotion of well-being in demanding educational or professional stages is essential to ensure optimal psychological development, and the GROW program has proved to be effective

in some groups so we believe that could be serve as tool for this objective (e.g., Tejada-Gallardo et al., 2020).

A previous pilot research of a program to promote well-being in PhD students (i.e., The Third Half) suggested how important it is for the academic community the implementation and evaluation of evidence-based psychological programs to support the mental health of researchers toward creating healthier workplaces among doctoral communities (Muro et al., 2022). For this reason, we aim to contribute to this important and necessary work which is being calling up.

Resources

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